

Skill Hierarchy Motivation Model for University Teachers In Indian Higher Education

Dr. Rajesh Tiwari

Associate Professor

*International Institute of Management Studies,
Pune*

Dr. Bimal Anjum

Assistant Professor,

DAV College, Chandigarh

Abstract: A country with young demographic profile has potential to transform the challenges into opportunities. The higher education system plays an important role to equip manpower with the skills to manage corporate sector, promote entrepreneurship and develop leaders for socio cultural transformation. The Indian higher education system has witnessed increasing influence of private sector in capacity building to provide access to students. Public sector institutions are constraints by declining budgetary allocations. Though private sector has increased the availability of seats for students, poor employability, and poor ranking of institutions in international rankings indicate that mere capacity expansion will not provide the optimum solutions for skill shortages but a robust higher education system led by highly motivated faculties. Despite salary increments in 6th pay commission, many institutions may only fifth pay commission in practice and show to the regulators that salary is being paid in accordance with 6th pay commission. Shortage of faculties in elite institutions indicates the lack of motivation to join teaching by talented individuals and neglect of teachers by management of institutions.

This paper is an attempt to explore the motivation in differences in satisfaction of academics in private and public sector universities. The academicians teaching in private and public universities in North India were considered for the study. The primary data was collected through questionnaires.

Results reveal that there are different motivators in private and public universities. Private university academicians were more influenced by intrinsic factors and public university academicians were more influenced by extrinsic factors. The Skill Hierarchy Motivation approach is recommended to motivate teachers at different level of skill and hierarchy.

Keywords: Motivation, Higher Education, North India, University, Teachers, Intrinsic, Extrinsic, Skill Hierarchy Motivation Model

INTRODUCTION:

India is facing unprecedented opportunity and challenge in human resource management. The country has 65% of its population is 35 years or below and 50% below 25 years (Virmani, 2014).

Such a human resource has the potential to transform economic, social, and technological growth by its creativity, energy and ambition. Efficient higher education system can transform this human resource into a creative asset to propel economy. But the challenge is shortage of good teachers. Recruitment is not the solution to teacher shortage, since 40 to 50 % new teachers leave the profession within a few years (Ingersoll and Smith 2003). The increases in across the board salaries instead of performance based and merit based salaries have been counterproductive as the policy have failed to attract good quality academicians. The increase in salaries in sixth pay commission in 2006 has been partially made redundant due to rising cost of living and inflation (Pushkar, 2012).

Objective:

Examine motivation of faculties in private and public sector Indian Higher Education Institution

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Role of Faculties:

The job satisfaction of university teachers has been neglected (Gaziel, 1986). Most of the studies on teacher satisfaction have been done in developed countries. Shortage of faculties is a result of neglect and low status of faculties in society. Poor status of teachers in society, and focus on business centric approach and ignoring human centric approach by the academic institutions, has led to neglect of teaching as a promising career option by the students. Higher education system has ignored the motivation of faculties (Rasheed et al. 2010). Majority of private higher education institutions treat their faculty like a bonded labour in matters of salary and service conditions (Agarwal, 2006). The role of faculty in higher education and their motivational aspects cannot be overlooked and time has come when human resource management in higher education industry should be redefined and rejuvenated (Varshney, 2012).

Motivation:

The study is based on job satisfaction literature. The Herzberg, Mausner, Snyderman (1959) as cited in Kadushin and Harkness (2002) two factor theory provides two set of factors. Extrinsic factors and intrinsic factors are two factors considered by Herzberg. Various researchers have attempted to study the satisfaction of academicians in universities. However there is no consensus about the factors that motivate academicians. Some author's support the Herzberg's approach (Sergiovani 1967, Strachan, 1975, Schmidt 1976, Gaziel, 1986, Syed, Bhatti, Michael, Shaikh, Shah, 2012, Gupta and Goel 2012) on the other hand other authors do not support the Herzberg's approach (Castillo and Cano 2004, Azmi & Sharma 2012). The studies indicate that satisfaction for academicians is a complex process and is multidimensional. There are demographic factors, cultural background and mixture of extrinsic and intrinsic factors that lead to satisfaction of academicians in universities.

Motivation of Teachers:

Poor salary, housing facilities, travel money, lack of respect in society, workload are causes for low motivation of teachers (Davidson 2007). Apart from compensation intangible factors like job design, work environment, feedback, recognition and empowerment or decision making participation are potential motivators for academicians in higher education (Rasheed et al. 2010). Organizational characteristics such as organizational climate, results, rewards and interpersonal relations, organizational processes, clarity of roles and sharing of information and altruistic behavior has emerged as a significant factor for job satisfaction (Kainth and Kaur 2010). Morale of teachers is coming down as compared to previous generations (Enders, 1997).

Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors:

Job satisfaction of a teacher is multidimensional and various factors affect the satisfaction simultaneously (Gautam and Dalal, 2006). Intrinsic factors like position may be used to overcome dissatisfaction (Moore, 2012). Chief academic officers and deans were dissatisfied with their nature of work (Glick, 1992). Tomas (2013) argued that most important reason for disengagement of employees is incompetent leadership. The personalities of supervisors and managers have a significant effect on level of engagement of employees.

Contrary to the unidimensional approach of Herzberg, Wickstorm (1971) as cited in Brown (2007) proposed that teacher satisfaction and dissatisfaction cannot be isolated into separate isolated features but the satisfaction depends on several factors which are interwoven. Schmidt (1976) also found that achievement, recognition, advancement motivates administrators. However Gaziel, (1986) found that responsibility is a source of dissatisfaction. Gaziel related it to tendency of the Principals to escape from

responsibility and place it with supervisors.

Work itself is the most motivating factor for university teachers (Mehboob et al. 2012) whereas working conditions is the least motivating factor (Castillo and Cano 2004). In contrast to Herzberg theory Castillo and Cano found that both hygiene and motivator factors were moderately related with overall job satisfaction. Faculty members enjoy having their independent scholarly pursuits and prefer to have a teaching load (Enders, 1997) that will allow them to pursue these projects (Gupta & Goel, 2012).

The sixth pay commission has increased the salaries significantly, but regular teachers are less motivated than non regular teachers (Kingdon, 2010). Teachers are more motivated by hygiene needs like money, so they move to high paying jobs (Bellot and Tutor 1990). Maidani (1991) compared satisfaction of private and public sector employees and found that public sector employees were more satisfied with extrinsic or hygiene factors as compared to private employees. Hygiene factors like salary, working conditions, and supervision is positively and significantly correlated with satisfaction for management faculties (Azmi, Sharma 2012).

Studies in North India:

The studies done in North India provide useful insight about the satisfaction of teachers in higher education. Gautam and Dalal (2006) studied satisfaction of teachers in Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Jammu. It was found that overall teachers had moderate level of job satisfaction. The young teachers were more satisfied than those teachers with longer period of service. Bakhshi et al. (2008) studied job satisfaction of teachers in private and government colleges in Jammu. It was found that teachers in government colleges were more satisfied as compared to teachers in private colleges.

Kainth and Kaur (2010) investigated satisfaction of teachers in affiliated colleges in Amritsar. It was found that teachers in rural areas were more satisfied than those in urban areas. Teachers in self financed colleges were more satisfied than those in government aided colleges. Deshwal (2011) examined job satisfaction of teachers in engineering colleges of Uttar Pradesh. The teachers were satisfied with work itself, student's interaction and reimbursement. It was found that participation of teachers in decision making can enhance satisfaction of teachers.

In another study on teacher motivation in North India, Varshney (2012) found that remuneration, responsibility and accomplishment were three most significant motivators. Lal and Shergill, (2012) found that in degree college teachers in Punjab and Haryana state of north India, no significant difference exists between male and

female teachers satisfaction. Both male and female teachers showed unfavorable attitude towards teaching. Azmi & Sharma (2012) found that pay, supervision and work schedule flexibility significantly influences the satisfaction of faculties in management institutes in UP and NCR region.

After review of literature following hypothesis has been generated

H1: There is no difference in motivational factors of teachers in public and private universities

Method:

The participants were teachers (faculties) teaching in private and public universities in north part of India. The participants were selected randomly different teaching departments of the universities. A survey design was used for the study. The primary data was collected through questionnaire. The data was analyzed using descriptive tests and t test to compare private and public universities.

Data Collection:

The primary data was collected by questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered personally and by post to 600 teachers. The pilot testing of the questionnaire was done on the respondents and based on the pilot testing and inputs of the senior academicians the final questionnaire was prepared. The respondents were asked to rank their satisfaction level on various parameters on a 5 point

Likert scale; strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), strongly agree (5). 326 questionnaires (196 males and 130 females) were returned by the respondents which represented a response rate of 54.33%. Out of 326 questionnaires 300 were considered for analysis. 26 questionnaires were incomplete and thus they were discarded. Field, Miles and Field (2012) considered a sample of 300 or more suitable to get a stable solution in factor analysis.

The internal validity of the motivation variables was verified using Cronback’s Alpha. Cronbach’s alpha is the most common measure of reliability (Field 2006). The Cronbach’s alpha value was obtained as .938 which was acceptable. Kline (2000) argued that reliability of 0.7 is a minimum for good test. Field (2006) argued that value between 0.7 and 0.8 is an acceptable value for Cronbach’s alpha. Cronbach’s alpha values more than 0.8 indicate good internal consistency. The Cronbach’s alpha values more than 0.9 give very good result, however it could indicate redundancy in the questionnaire (Curtis, Drannan 2013).

RESULTS:

The descriptive statistics and t test was used to compare the satisfaction of private and public university faculties. Table 1 shows the summary of demographic profile of respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

		Percentage			Percentage
Type of Organization	Private	52%	Teaching Experience (Years)	1-3	3.33%
	Public	48%		4-6	24.33%
Gender	Male	60%		7-10	34%
	Female	40%		11-15	27.67%
Qualification	PhD	74.67%		16-20	7.67%
	Post Graduate	25.33%		21-25	1.67%
Academic Title	Professor	20%		More than 25	1.33%
	Associate Professor	26.33%	Industry Experience (Years)	Nil	66.67%
	Assistant Professor	53.67%	1-5 Years	21%	
			6-10 Years	11.67%	
			11-15 Years	0.03%	
			16-20 Years	0.03%	

The mean value of extrinsic factors for private universities was obtained as 3.24, and for public universities it was 3.79. The mean value for intrinsic

factor was 3.76 for private university and 3.56 for public universities.

The mean suggest that the respondents of private university (Mean 3.76) were more satisfied with intrinsic factors as compared to respondents of public university (Means 3.26). However the respondents in public university (Mean 3.79) were more satisfied with extrinsic factors than respondents of private university (Mean 3.24). The salary and working conditions in public universities are found to be better as compared to the public universities.

Exploratory factor analysis was done separately on private and public universities. The principal component factor analysis was used for the study. The factor analysis Sampling adequacy was assessed using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure. Field (2013) cited Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999) to describe significance of KMO values. Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999) considered KMO values in 0.90s as marvelous, 0.80s as meritorious, 0.70s as middling, 0.60s as mediocre, 0.50s as miserable, below 0.50 as unacceptable. KMO values varied from 0.821 to

0.888. The values belong to the meritorious category of Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999). To check suitability of data for factor analysis, Bartlett's test of sphericity was used. The Bartlett's test of sphericity was found to be significant ($p < 0.05$), thus factor analysis was considered appropriate

Table 2: KMO, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Variable	Org.	KMO	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Sig.)
Motivation	Private	0.857	0.00
	Public	0.888	0.00

Table 3 shows the variable loadings for each factor after rotation. Components with factor loadings of 0.5 and above have been considered for inclusion in a factor.

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix for Motivation in Private Universities

Rotated Component Matrix (RCM) ^a				
	Factors			
	Work Itself & Esteem (FACPR1)	Recognition and Co-worker relations (FACPR 2)	Pay and Policy (FACPR 3)	Achievement (FACPR 4)
Enthusiasm for Job (MT1)	.919			
Job Provides a sense of Pride (MT2)	.854			
I have a fair chance of Promotion (MT3)	.936			
Good Performers are promoted (MT4)	.860			
Good Performers get recognition (MT5)		.930		
I am recognized for my achievements (MT6)		.920		
I am happy with responsibilities allocated to me (MT7)	.933			
I have autonomy to accomplish my responsibilities (MT8)	.925			
Organizational support is provided for professional development (MT9)				.813
Professional Achievements are rewarded (MT10)				.833
Organization pays fair salary to me (MT11)			.833	
Organization provides opportunities for salary hike (MT12)			.824	
Faculty needs are understood by supervisor (MT13)		.923		
Supervisor is able to guide properly in official matters (MT14)		.924		
I have satisfactory professional relationship with teachers of my department (MT15)		.893		
I have satisfactory professional relationship with other staff members (MT16)		.882		
Rules and Regulations for teachers are sensible (MT17)			.857	
I am satisfied with rules and regulations for teachers (MT18)			.907	

Workload is satisfactory (MT19)			.867	
Job security is satisfactory (MT20)			.848	
Eigen Value	9.311	3.653	3.125	1.048
Percentage of Variance Explained	46.56%	18.26%	15.62%	5.24%
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.				

Table 4 shows the variable loadings for each factor after rotation for public universities. Components with factor loadings of 0.5 and above have been considered for inclusion in a factor.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix for Motivation in Public Universities

Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
	Factors			
	Esteem (FACPB1)	Pay and Policy (FACPB2)	Coworker relation (FACPB3)	Work Itself (FACPB4)
Enthusiasm for Job (MT1)				.853
Job Provides a sense of Pride (MT2)				.846
I have a fair chance of Promotion (MT3)	.951			
Good Performers are promoted (MT4)	.934			
Good Performers get recognition (MT5)	.920			
I am recognized for my achievements (MT6)	.936			
I am happy with responsibilities allocated to me (MT7)	.936			
I have autonomy to accomplish my responsibilities (MT8)	.939			
Organizational support is provided for professional development (MT9)	.933			
Professional Achievements are rewarded (MT10)	.939			
Organization pays fair salary to me (MT11)		.869		
Organization provides opportunities for salary hike (MT12)		.882		
Faculty needs are understood by supervisor (MT13)			.942	
Supervisor is able to guide properly in official matters (MT14)			.930	
I have satisfactory professional relationship with teachers of my department (MT15)			.941	
I have satisfactory professional relationship with other staff members (MT16)			.929	
Rules and Regulations for teachers are sensible (MT17)		.887		
I am satisfied with rules and regulations for teachers (MT18)		.901		
Workload is satisfactory (MT19)		.920		
Job security is satisfactory (MT20)		.886		
Eigen Value	10.69	3.71	2.91	1.05
Percentage of Variance Explained	53.48%	18.56%	14.55%	5.29%
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.				

The result of t test for variables with clustered together to form a factor are done first and then variables that do not cluster together in a factor are done later. Table 5 shows the t test for variables M3, M4, M7, and M8.

Table 5: T Test for Variables common in factor FACPR 1 and FACPB1

	T	df	Sig	Mean Diff.
MT3	5.946	298	0.000	0.74
MT4	5.952	298	0.000	0.73
MT7	5.368	298	0.000	0.67
MT8	5.911	298	0.000	0.73

The p value (0.00) is less than 0.05 thus it is concluded that a significant difference exists between private and public universities. Table 6 shows the t test for variables MT11, MT12, MT17, MT18, MT19 and MT20. These variables clustered together to form factor in public (FACPB2) and private (FACPR3) university

Table 6: T Test for Variables common in factor FACPR 3 and FACPB2

	T	df	Sig	Mean Diff.
MT11	-5.338	298	.000	-.623
MT12	-5.258	298	.000	-.616
MT17	-6.281	298	.000	-.694
MT18	-6.229	298	.000	-.683
MT19	-6.609	298	.000	-.696
MT20	-6.201	298	.000	-.649

The p value (0.00) is less than 0.05 so it is inferred that there is a significant difference between private and public universities.

Table 7: T Test for Variables common in factor FACPR 2 and FACPB3

	T	Df	Sigg	Mean Difference
MT13	-2.347	298	.020	-.308
MT14	-2.820	298	.005	-.354
MT15	-3.375	298	.001	-.405
MT16	-3.278	298	.001	-.399

Private and public universities show a significant difference as P value is less than 0.05.

Table 8: T Test for Variables in different factors in private and public universities

	T	df	Sig	Mean Diff.
MT1	-3.299	298	.001	-.347
MT2	-3.120	298	.002	-.364
MT5	-1.130	298	.260	-.150
MT6	-1.081	298	.281	-.149
MT9	1.285	298	.200	.175
MT10	-.032	298	.975	-.004

The p value is less than 0.05 for MT1 and MT2, thus it is inferred that a significant difference exists between private and public universities for sense of enthusiasm (MT1) and sense of pride (MT2) of about job. However for other four variables (MT10, MT9, MT6, MT5) no significant difference was found ($P > 0.05$)

Except four variables it is found that value is less than 0.05 and thus null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a difference in the motivational tool in public and private universities faculties.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The unique nature of teaching makes traditional approaches of motivation less effective. The complexity of work, difficulty in quantifying objectives and lack of traditional subordinate supervisor relationships require different approach to motivate teachers. The motivational approaches that work well for a lower level of hierarchy may not work for a teacher in higher level of hierarchy, similarly motivational approach for a teacher with low skills may not work for a teacher with high skills. A skill hierarchy matrix is proposed to motivate teachers in Indian higher education system. The levels of hierarchy are shown on vertical axis and levels of skill are shown on horizontal axis. The level of hierarchy is divided into three levels; low, medium and high. Similarly level of skill is divided into three levels; low, medium and high.

SKILL HIERARCHY MOTIVATION MODEL:

The skill hierarchy motivation model assumes that extrinsic and intrinsic factors work together to motivate a teacher. The effect of the motivational tool can lead to movement of a faculty in three directions. A faculty from existing position may move vertically and reach higher level of hierarchy or move horizontally and enhance the level of skill. A faculty may also move diagonally and enhance both the level of hierarchy and level of skill.

Figure 3: Skill Hierarchy Motivation Model for Teachers in Indian Higher Education

Source: Conceptualized by Researcher

The effect of the motivational tool can lead to movement of a faculty in three directions. A faculty from existing position may move vertically and reach higher level of hierarchy or move horizontally and enhance the level of skill. A faculty may also move diagonally and enhance both the level of hierarchy and level of skill.

LOW SKILL -LOW HIERARCHY:

The teachers at low levels of skill joining the teaching profession can be motivated by offering them learning opportunities by providing *skill enhancement training*. The teachers would be provided skill enhancement training if they are making good attempt in producing good academic results of students, and make an attempt for publications and involve themselves in other enhance the effectiveness of organization and student learning experience. At this level skill enhancement as an incentive is beneficial for both the institution and teacher. The teacher becomes more valuable by acquiring skills and organization becomes more valuable by having a more skilled teachers. Incremental education motivates younger employees (Fertik, 2011).

MEDIUM SKILL-LOW HIERARCHY:

As a result of skills enhancement training the faculty makes a progression from a low skill level to a medium skill level, while remaining at a low hierarchy level. At this position faculty can be motivated by providing *growth opportunities* to move up the hierarchy level based on performance. The fair promotions will not only motivate teachers but will attract talented individuals into teaching.

Faculty at medium skill and low hierarchy can move up to medium hierarchy while remaining at medium skill level or can move from medium skill level to high skill level, while remaining at low hierarchy level. Lack of opportunity for growth in the organization relative to

skills will guide movement of faculty from low skill level to high skill level at same hierarchy or low hierarchy to medium hierarchy at same skill level.

HIGH SKILL-LOW HIERARCHY:

To attract talented individuals having high skills in teaching, a performance based pay motivation tool can be used. The existing teachers with high skills but working at low hierarchy can be motivated by providing *performance based pay*. The pay for teachers in Indian higher education is fixed according to qualification at entry level and low hierarchy positions. The annual increments are done according to performance. The good performers and poor performers get essentially the same pay. Thus there is no driving force (motivation) for teachers with high skills to make efforts. They tend to withdraw from making any extra effort to show good performers. Thus providing performance based pay can motivate such teachers.

The performance can be quantified for incentives. The broad parameters for such incentives could be publication in high impact journals, enhancing employability skills of students, number of projects for industry collaboration, innovation in teaching and operational systems, number of sponsored research projects, consultancy, student feedback, academic performance of students.

HIGH SKILL- MEDIUM HIERARCHY:

The effect of motivation due to performance based pay can make the teachers with high skill working at low hierarchy, a suitable candidate for promoting them to medium level of hierarchy. Once these teachers will progress to medium level of hierarchy they can be motivated further by providing them *growth opportunities*. Such growth opportunities can motivate the teachers with high skill and medium level of hierarchy to put extra effort and move up to high level of hierarchy.

HIGH SKILL- HIGH HIERARCHY

Once the teacher with high skill reaches the high level of hierarchy, they can be motivated by providing them *autonomy*. Majority of institution heads in Indian higher education institutions want to leverage their experience and talent to enhance the relevance of their institutions in research, academic outcomes of students, industry collaboration and international ranking but lack of autonomy restricts such an endeavor. The bureaucrats have kept the decision making powers with them and allowed heads of institutions to just remain a rubber stamp to follow the dictates of the bureaucracy and/or politicians. Providing autonomy to teachers at high level of hierarchy will unleash their creativity and they can leverage their experience, academic acumen, and vision to create world class institutions. The autonomy will motivate them to go further to achieve satisfaction of building up a world class institution.

MEDIUM SKILL-MEDIUM HIERARCHY:

A Teacher with medium skill and at low hierarchy can move to a medium hierarchy while remaining at medium skill. Some teachers at low skill and low hierarchy can also move up directly to medium skill and medium hierarchy. Such a movement is dependent on capability of a person to learn and availability of opportunities to move up to a medium level of hierarchy within an organization. Once a teacher reaches the medium skill medium hierarchy cell, that teacher can be motivated by providing *collaboration*. Such collaborations will be multiple levels involving faculties in foreign institutions, research projects with industry or other high ranking institutions. Collaboration will support the fulfillment of broader goals rather than just producing graduates. Growth opportunities will motivate to put extra effort to show good performance and move up to high level of hierarchy.

MEDIUM SKILL-HIGH HIERARCHY

The teacher at medium skill high hierarchy level can move in three directions. Horizontal movement to high skill while continuing at medium level of hierarchy. Vertical movement can lead to progression from medium hierarchy to high hierarchy. Diagonal movement can provide enhancement in both level of skill and level of hierarchy to progress the teacher to high skill high hierarchy cell. The direction of movement will depend on capability of teacher to enhance skills and availability of opportunities within organization for moving up to a higher level of skill.

Once the teacher reaches the medium skill high hierarchy cell, the teacher can be motivated to put extra efforts by motivating with *benchmarking*. Since the teacher has reached high hierarchy motivation by providing incentives once the performance of the institution is enhanced as compared to that of the institution chosen as the benchmark. The institution selected as benchmark

should be the market leader in that discipline.

LOW SKILL-MEDIUM HIERARCHY:

The faculty at low skill and low hierarchy may move to medium hierarchy after skill enhancement training, though remaining at low level of skill. In such a case the faculty can be motivated by *coaching and mentoring* strategy. As the enhancement in hierarchy provides greater responsibilities, such teachers requires coaching to provide them support and encouragement to put extra effort and move up the hierarchy. Their performance can be monitored on a regular basis to motivate them to perform better and coaching is provided in case of some shortfall. In Indian Context, coaching and mentoring by experienced teachers can instill self confidence in young teachers to develop independence of thought and challenge the applicability of Western theories in Indian Context (Panda and Gupta, 2014).

LOW SKILL- HIGH HIERARCHY

When a teacher with low skill reaches high hierarchy, the teacher can be motivated by collaboration. The collaboration will provide the support in terms of high skills of teachers from high ranking institution. On the other hand high ranking institution can benefit by leveraging the high hierarchy of the teacher to explore mutually beneficial association in terms of getting access to more number of students, high skill teachers and research collaborations.

Limitations:

The study covers public and private university faculties in North part of the country including eight states. The findings of the study may not be generalized for all private and public universities in India. The study considered teachers of public and private institutions only. The findings may not be applicable to private and public colleges affiliated to universities and autonomous higher education institutions. The results may vary for other regions of the country. The findings need to be validated by a larger sample including teachers from affiliated colleges; autonomous institutions to provide a better understanding about factor that motivate teachers in these institutions. The results may not be generalized outside India. The data is self reported. There is a risk of bias, selective recall, and multicollinearity. The study has collected data only from faculties and has not considered the viewpoints of administrators, students.

Implications for further research:

The applicability of skill hierarchy motivation model needs to be studied for teachers in different types of institutions in Indian higher education; central universities, deemed to be universities, affiliated colleges, government aided colleges and institutes of national importance. Variability across different disciplines may also be studied.

Implications for Practice: The findings have several implications for academic leaders and regulatory agencies monitoring higher education system in India. The findings indicate that management of private universities has ignored recognition of teachers. Public universities provide relaxed working conditions and job security, it may not be sufficient to motivate teachers. Despite significant increase in salaries after implementation of sixth pay commission, there is no significant increase in academic outcomes of Indian universities. Ignoring the intrinsic factors recognition, responsibility, advancement opportunities can limit the impact of better working conditions in public universities. Better academic and research output of teachers working in autonomous institutions support the significance of intrinsic factors for motivating teachers. Indian higher education system is suffering on one side by shortage of good quality teachers and low motivation of existing teachers. To bring vibrancy into the system of higher education motivation strategy that takes care of the skill and hierarchy profile of teacher should be adopted. The skill hierarchy motivation model provides opportunity to enhance the relevance of bottom of the pyramid higher education institutions and for few elite institutions to enhance their international recognition and ranking.

REFERENCES:

- [1]. Agarwal, P. (2006). Higher education in India: the need for change. Working paper 180, *Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations*, accessed on October, 11 2017, from http://www.icrier.org/pdf/ICRIER_WP180__Higher_Education_in_India.pdf
- [2]. Azmi, T., & Sharma, M. (2012). Job related dimensions and faculty members satisfaction at Indian business schools: An empirical study. *International Journal of Management Business and Research*, 2(1), 23-40, accessed on February 16, 2017, through www.ijmbr.org/?_action=showPDF&article=50&_ob...
- [3]. Bakhshi, A., Sharma, A., Sharma, S., & Kumar, K. (2008). Job satisfaction as predictor of life satisfaction: A study on lecturers in government and private colleges in Jammu, accessed on September 25, 2015 from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1409362
- [4]. Bellot, F. K., & Tutor, F. D. (1990), A challenge to the conventional wisdom of Herzberg and Maslow theories, Paper presented at Annual Meeting of Mid-South Educational Research Association, New Orleans, LA, November 14-16.
- [5]. Brown, T. (2007). Teacher motivation in Arkansas schools, UMI 3295015, Proquest Information and Learning Company
- [6]. Castillo, J., & Cano, J. (2004). Factors explaining job satisfaction among faculty, *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 45(3), accessed 10th October 2016 from http://pubs.aged.tamu.edu/jae/pdf/Vol45/45-03-065.pdf?origin=publication_detail
- [7]. Curtis, E., & Drennan, J. (2013). *Quantitative Health Research: Issues and Methods*, Open University Press, Mc Graw Hill Education, Berkshire, p 320
- [8]. Davidson, E. (2007). The pivotal role of teacher motivation in Tanzanian education. *The Educational Forum*, 157-166, Kappa Delta Pi, International Honor Society in Education, Canada, accessed October 10, 2017 from http://hakielimu.org/files/publications/document100pivot_al_role_teacher_motivation_en.pdf
- [9]. Deshwal, P. (2011). Job satisfaction: A study of those who mould the future of India. Global Conference on Innovations in Management London, UK.
- [10]. Enders, J. (1997). The academic profession in Europe: A view from the status perspective, CERT Discussion Paper 97/18, accessed on September 24, 2016 from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=85948
- [11]. Fertik, M. (2011). Managing and motivating employees in their twenties. *Harvard Business Review*, accessed September 26, 2015 from <https://hbr.org/2011/01/managing-employees-in-their-tw/>
- [12]. Field, A. (2006). Reliability analysis, accessed October 12 2017 from <http://www.statisticshell.com/docs/reliability.pdf>
- [13]. Field, A., Miles, J., & Field, Z. (2012), *Discovering Statistics Using R*, Sage Publications Pvt Ltd, New Delhi.
- [14]. Gautam, M. M. K., & Dalal R. S. (2006). Job satisfaction of faculty members of veterinary sciences: An analysis. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 18(6).
- [15]. Gaziel, H. H. (1986). Correlates of job satisfaction: a study of two factor theory in an educational setting. *The Journal of Psychology*, 120(6), 613-626.
- [16]. Glick, N. L. (1992). Job satisfaction among academic administrators. *Research in Higher Education*, 33(5), 625-639.
- [17]. Gupta, S., & Goel, P. (2012). Relationship between faculty & student satisfaction for better results in management education. *International Journal of Research Review in Engineering Science and Technology*, 1(1), 62-64,
- [18]. Ingersoll, R., & Smith, T. (2003). The wrong solution to the teacher shortage. *Educational Leadership*, 60(8), 30-33.
- [19]. Kadushin, A., & Harkness, D. (2002). *Supervision in Social Work*, Columbia University Press, 4th Edition, New York
- [20]. Kainth, G. S., & Kaur, G. (2010). Job satisfaction: a challenging area of research in education, Munich Personal RePEc Archive, Paper No. 29667, accessed on October 10, 2017 from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1784465
- [21]. Kingdon, G. (2010). The impact of the sixth pay commission on teacher salaries: assessing equity and efficiency effects. RECOUP Working Paper No. 29, Research Consortium on Educational Outcomes and Poverty, accessed on October 11, 2014 from http://ceid.educ.cam.ac.uk/publications/WP29_GK_SixthPay.pdf
- [22]. Kline, P. (2000), *Handbook of Psychological Testing*, Routledge, London
- [23]. Lal, R., & Shergill, S. S. (2012). A comparative study of

- job satisfaction towards education among male and female teachers of degree colleges. *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services and Management Research*, 1(1).
- [24]. Maidani, E. (1991). Comparative study of Herzberg's two-factor theory of job satisfaction among public and private sectors, *Public Personnel Management*, 20(4), 441-448.
- [25]. Mehboob, F., Sarwar, M. A., & Bhutto, N.A. (2012). Factors affecting job satisfaction among faculty members: Herzberg's two factor theory perspective, A study of Shah Abdul Latif University Sind, Pakistan, *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 1(12), 1-9.
- [26]. Moore, H. L. (2012). Ethical climate, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction of full-time faculty members, Doctoral Dissertation, East Tennessee State University, accessed 15th July 2016 from <http://dc.etsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2600&context=etd>
- [27]. Panda, A., & Gupta R. K. (2014). Making academic research more relevant: A few suggestions, *IIMB Management Review*, 26(3), 156-169.
- [28]. Pushkar, P. (2012). In search of India's 'missing' professors, the chronicle of higher education, accessed July 25 2012 from <http://chronicle.com/blogs/worldwise/in-search-of-indias-missing-professors/29238>
- [29]. Rasheed, M, I., Aslam D. H., & Sarwar S. (2010). Motivational issues for teachers in higher education: A critical case of IUB, *Journal of Management Research*, 2010, 2(2).
- [30]. Schmidt, G. L. (1976). Job satisfaction among secondary school administrators, *Educational Administration Quarterly* 12 (2), 68-86.
- [31]. Sergiovanni, T. (1967). Factors which affect satisfaction and dissatisfaction of teachers, *Journal of Educational Administration*, 5(1), 66-82.
- [32]. Strachan, E. (1975). An application of Herzberg's motivator-hygiene theory to teacher job satisfaction, Master Thesis, University of Ottawa, accessed on November 2017 from <http://www.ruor.uottawa.ca/bitstream/10393/22328/1/EC56212.PDF>
- [33]. Syed, A, Bhatti, N., Michael S., Shaikh F, Shah H., (2012). Job satisfaction of faculty members of universities in Pakistan: a case study of University of Sindh-Jamshoro, *Modern Applied Science*; 6(7).
- [34]. Tomas, C. (2013). Does Money Really Affect Motivation? A Review of Research, *Harvard Business Review*, accessed 15th August 2017 from <https://hbr.org/2013/04/does-money-really-affect-motiv>
- [35]. Varshney, D. (2011). A Study of motivational and role dynamics in higher education, *International Journal of Research in Commerce, Economics, and Management*, 1(7)
- [36]. Virmani, P. (2014). Note to India's leaders: your 150m young people are calling for change, *The Guardian*, accessed on December 2017 from <http://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2014/apr/08/india-leaders-young-people-change-2014-election>